

*miRNA-XXX: a new player regulating skin homeostasis
and Atopic Dermatitis*

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by

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Abstract

There is no single cause of eczema. It probably has a mixture of inherited and environmental causes that act together at different times. The roles of miRNAs in the disease are not clearly defined. Originally identified as moderate biological modifiers, microRNAs have recently emerged as powerful regulators of diverse cellular processes with especially important roles in disease and tissue remodeling. Narrowing down a list of differentially expressed candidates in patients with atopic dermatitis we landed into the genomic locus of miR-XXX. Coupled with my finding that overexpression of miR-XXX in human keratinocytes promotes differentiation by causing cell cycle arrest *in vitro* and the down regulation of miR-XXX in lesional skin of atopic dermatitis displaying altered differentiation/hyperproliferation, I conclude miR-XXX as an important regulator of keratinocyte differentiation in normal skin, deregulation of which is likely the cause of hyperproliferation in atopic dermatitis. My findings raises hope finding potentially new therapeutics for skin disorders relating to inflammation, by restoring the levels of miR-XXX.

Atopic Dermatitis

Atopic Dermatitis (AD) is a severe form of dermatitis characterized by atopy. “Atopy” refers to a tendency to develop hypersensitive allergy conditions. “Dermatitis” is the condition in skin (Dermis) in which it becomes red, swollen, and sore. This is a long term (Chronic Inflammatory) skin disease commonly known as Atopic Eczema or Eczema that often precedes asthma and allergic disorders (Bieber 2008). “Eczema” is a term for many kinds of skin problems. Atopic dermatitis is the most common kind.

The hallmarks of atopic dermatitis are a chronic, relapsing form of skin inflammation, a disturbance of epidermal-barrier function that culminates in dry skin, and IgE-mediated sensitization to food and environmental allergens (Boguniewicz and Leung). The clinical manifestations of atopic dermatitis vary with age; three stages can often be identified. In infancy, the first eczematous lesions usually emerge on the cheeks and the scalp. Scratching, which frequently starts a few weeks later, causes crusted erosions. During childhood, lesions involve flexures, the nape, and the dorsal aspects of the limbs. In adolescence and adulthood, lichenified plaques affect the flexures, head, and neck (Sehra, Tuana et al. 2008). In each stage, itching that continues throughout the day and worsens at night causes sleep loss and substantially impairs the patient’s quality of life.

Who Gets Atopic Dermatitis?

AD affects both sexes equally. Its prevalence has increased two- to threefold during the past three decades in industrialized countries affecting 15 to 30% of children and 2 to 10% of adults; but remains much lower in countries with predominantly rural or agricultural areas. This frequently starts in early infancy (so-called early-onset atopic dermatitis). A total of 45% of all cases of atopic dermatitis begin within the first 6 months of life, 60% begin during the first year, and 85% begin before 5 years of age (Bieber 2008). More than 50% of children who are affected in the first 2 years of life do not have any sign of IgE sensitization, but they become sensitized during the course of atopic dermatitis. IgE does gate keeper function. Up to 70% of these children have a spontaneous remission before adolescence. The disease can also start in adults (so-called late-onset atopic dermatitis), and in a substantial number of these patients there is no sign of IgE-mediated sensitization (Sehra, Tuana et al. 2008). Wide variations in prevalence have been observed within countries inhabited by groups with similar genetic backgrounds, suggesting that environmental factors play a critical role in determining expression of AD. The lower prevalence of atopic dermatitis in rural as compared with urban areas suggests a link to the “hygiene hypothesis,” which postulates that the absence of early childhood exposure to infectious agents increases susceptibility to allergic diseases (Simon and Bieber). This concept has recently been questioned with regard to atopic dermatitis, however.

What Causes Atopic Dermatitis?

The cause of atopic dermatitis is not yet known. It is likely to be caused by both genetic (runs in the family) and environmental factors. People with atopic dermatitis may go on to develop hay fever and asthma.

Two hypotheses concerning the mechanism of atopic dermatitis have been proposed. One holds that the primary defect resides in an immunologic disturbance that causes IgE-mediated sensitization, with epithelial-barrier dysfunction regarded as a consequence of the local inflammation. The other proposes that an intrinsic defect in the epithelial cells leads to the barrier dysfunction; the immunologic aspects are considered to be an epiphenomenon (Bieber 2008).

Atopic Dermatitis – Phenotype

The skin is a frequent site of hypersensitivity reactions against apparently harmless antigens, such as the haptens causing allergic contact dermatitis (ACD), and of relapsing-remitting chronic disorders resulting from altered immune responses to environmental factors, such as atopic dermatitis (AD). Although both ACD and AD diseases are driven by T cells and characterized by eczematous changes in the epidermis, the clinical features of these skin diseases as well as the pathogenetic mechanisms leading to disease expression are substantially different. In fact, although ACD affects adults primarily and occurs in the skin at sites of contact with haptens, AD usually develops in early childhood with a characteristic distribution pattern that changes with age, and is frequently associated with respiratory atopy and elevated serum levels of immunoglobulin E (IgE) reactive to environmental protein allergens (Eyerich, Onken et al.). In addition, genetic factors are certainly very important in the development of AD whereas they have limited relevance in ACD (Williams and Flohr 2006).

The intrinsic capacity to respond to trigger factors can be shared in both the diseases. Among them, the most intriguing pathological aspect common to both allergic skin disorders is the prominent proinflammatory activity of resident keratinocytes, which serve as initiators and amplifiers of local immune responses. During ACD and atopic dermatitis development, in fact, keratinocytes sense haptens or environmental protein allergens, respectively, and, in turn, initiate a program of enhanced or de-novo expression of inflammatory molecules representing the starting point of primary skin inflammation. Furthermore, the prominent presence of T-cell infiltrate in both ACD and atopic dermatitis skin establishes an inflammatory cytokine micromilieu responsible for the massive activation of keratinocytes. Following exposure to T cell-derived lymphokines, keratinocytes express a plethora of cytokines, chemokines and accessory receptors, which potently amplifies immune responses of innate and adaptive skin immunity (Strachan 1989).

Lymphokines and cytokines released by T lymphocytes and other immune cells represent the most important stimuli that elicit the inflammatory activation of keratinocytes. Depending on the type and extent of T-cell infiltrate present in allergic contact dermatitis and atopic dermatitis skin lesions, keratinocytes are exposed to different cytokine microenvironment and, in turn, produce inflammatory mediators qualitatively and quantitatively specific for each disease. Keratinocyte-derived inflammatory molecules amplify skin immune responses associated with allergic contact dermatitis and atopic dermatitis, and contribute to the disease process and clinical phenotype development (Albanesi 2010).

Keratinocyte contributing to the pathogenesis of atopic dermatitis

Keratinocyte is the predominant cell type in the epidermis, the outermost layer of the skin, constituting 90% of the cells found there. Those keratinocytes found in the basal layer (Stratum basale) of the skin are sometimes referred to as "basal cells" or "basal keratinocytes". The primary function of keratinocytes is the formation of a barrier against environmental damage such as pathogens (bacteria, fungi, parasites, viruses), heat, UV radiation and water loss. Once pathogens start to invade the upper layers of the epidermis, keratinocytes can react with the production of proinflammatory mediators and in particular chemokines such as CXCL10, CCL2 which attract leukocytes to the site of pathogen invasion. A number of structural proteins (filaggrin, keratin), enzymes (proteases), lipids and antimicrobial peptides (defensins) contribute to maintain the important barrier function of the skin. Keratinization is part of the physical barrier formation (cornification), in which the keratinocytes produce more and more keratin and undergo terminal differentiation. The fully cornified keratinocytes that form the outermost layer are constantly shed off and replaced by new cells (Pastore, Mascia et al. 2006).

An amount of evidence defines keratinocytes as enhancer cells of immune responses in atopic dermatitis. Owing to their altered genetic background, keratinocytes of atopic dermatitis skin respond peculiarly and excessively to environmental stimuli and to endogenous T cell-derived cytokines. In-vitro studies have shown that keratinocytes from patients with atopic dermatitis produce increased amounts of certain types of chemokines and cytokines compared with healthy cells or keratinocytes isolated from psoriatic skin. For instance, atopic dermatitis keratinocytes are a source of CCL5 when activated in vitro with IFN-g or TNF- α , probably as a consequence of a functional mutation in CCL5 gene (Homey, Alenius et al. 2002), (Nomura, Gao et al. 2003). CCL5 is also strongly expressed in basal keratinocytes in atopic dermatitis skin in vivo and may have a role in promoting the accumulation of Th1 lymphocytes in the chronic phase of the disease. Keratinocytes cultured from patients with atopic dermatitis overproduce CCL20 (Gunther, Bello-Fernandez et al. 2005). Interestingly, disruption of the epidermal permeability barrier upregulates expression of CCL20, revealing an important mechanism for the initial influx of dendritic cells and T cells in the skin of patients with atopic dermatitis. Similarly to ACD lesions, both acute and chronic atopic dermatitis lesions exhibit strong expression of CCL27 in the epidermis as well as many CCR10⁺ T cells (Albanesi, Scarponi et al. 2005). When compared with keratinocytes from non-atopic individuals, keratinocytes of atopic dermatitis patients produce higher levels of GM-CSF and TNF- α , both basally and in response to IL-1 or IFN-g (Pivarcsi, Gombert et al. 2004). Elevated production of cytokines by atopic dermatitis keratinocytes may be secondary to dysregulated signal transduction.

It is well known that patients with atopic dermatitis frequently have bacterial and viral skin infections (Gombert, Dieu-Nosjean et al. 2005) (Echigo, Hasegawa et al. 2004). For instance, atopic dermatitis skin is heavily colonized by superantigen-releasing *Staphylococcus aureus*, which is able to induce the expansion of specific T cell subpopulations (Jost, Kari et al. 2000), and to stimulate an IgE mediated hyperreactivity response (Lukacs, Miller et al. 2003). In addition, herpes simplex virus infections of the skin occur frequently in atopic dermatitis. This predisposition to cutaneous infections can be related to a substantial deficiency of innate protective mechanisms in atopic dermatitis skin. In particular, a set of antimicrobial peptides, namely HBD2, HBD3 and LL-37, are significantly decreased in keratinocytes of atopic dermatitis patients. This reduced expression of antimicrobial peptides was found to be an acquired rather than intrinsic defect, as a result of the increased Th2 cytokine expression in atopic dermatitis skin. The enhanced bacterial and viral dissemination in patients with atopic dermatitis has also been associated with a compromised status of the epidermal barrier. Several recent studies have demonstrated an association between atopic dermatitis and decreased keratinocyte expression of filaggrin (FLG), a protein of the epidermal differentiation complex involved in barrier function. In particular, null mutations in the gene that encodes FLG were shown to be linked to the phenotype of atopic dermatitis and asthma-associated atopic dermatitis whereas no associations were observed with psoriasis. However, these mutations have been observed in less than one third of general populations of atopic dermatitis patients of European descent (Mascia, Mariani et al. 2003) (Pastore, Mascia et al. 2005). Additionally, these mutations were heterozygous in most cases. Indeed, Howell et al. (Howell, Fairchild et al. 2008) demonstrated that FLG deficiency in patients with atopic dermatitis is owing to the overexpression of Th2 cytokines, which downregulate FLG during the differentiation process. Therefore, it is likely that many patients with atopic dermatitis acquire FLG deficiency and subsequent barrier disruption as a result of the local inflammatory immune responses. Similarly to FLG, other proteins of the epidermal differentiation complex, namely loricrin, involucrin, and late cornified envelope proteins, had reduced or compromised levels of expression in lesional atopic dermatitis skin [38]. The dysfunction of epidermal barrier in atopic dermatitis has also been associated with an abnormal serine protease activity in the epidermis. In particular, Hansson et al. (Hansson, Backman et al. 2002) found that a transgenic mouse model overexpressing human stratum corneum chymotryptic enzyme (SCCE) exhibited symptoms of chronic itchy dermatitis resembling atopic dermatitis. Being SCCE active also in the proteolytic degradation of distinct lipid processing enzymes, including acidic sphingomyelinase, enhanced SCCE could reasonably provide a direct link between enhanced serine protease activity and reduced ceramide expression in atopic dermatitis skin. The importance of regulated proteolysis in epithelia is well demonstrated by the discovery of the lympho-epithelial kazal-type 5 serine protease inhibitor (LEKTI), encoded by the Spink5 gene (Soumelis, Reche et al. 2002).

LEKTI defective inhibitory regulation results in increased protease activity in the stratum corneum and overdesquamation of corneocytes, as demonstrated in Netherton disease. LEKTI is strongly expressed in differentiated keratinocytes of normal skin and contribute to the integrity and protective barrier function of the skin. Previously, Walley et al. identified six polymorphisms in Spink5 gene and found that a particular variant (Glu420Lys) in LEKTI significantly associated with atopy, including atopic dermatitis (Walley, Chavanas et al. 2001).

The Biology of miRNAs:

MicroRNAs are a family of small, non-coding RNAs (sizing ~19–25 nt) that regulate gene expression in a sequence-specific manner. The two founding members of the microRNA family were originally identified in *Caenorhabditis elegans* as genes that were required for the timed regulation of developmental events (Lee, Feinbaum et al. 1993). Since then, hundreds of microRNAs have been identified in almost all metazoan genomes, including worms, flies, plants and mammals. MicroRNAs have diverse expression patterns and might regulate various developmental and physiological processes. Their discovery adds a new dimension to our understanding of complex gene regulatory networks.

miRNA – the name:

A system of nomenclature has been adopted and names are designated to specific miRNAs before publication of their discovery as hundreds of human miRNAs and thousands across other species are available as of now (Griffiths-Jones, Grocock et al. 2006). Experimentally confirmed microRNAs are given a number that is attached to the prefix mir followed by a dash e.g. mir-123. The uncapitalised mir-refers to the pre-miRNA and the capitalised miR- refers to the mature form. miRNAs with similar structures bar at 1 or 2 nucleotides are annotated to show their similar structure with added lower case letter e.g. miR-1a and miR-1b.

It is possible for miRNAs at different loci to produce the same miRNA and these are show with additional number eg miR-1-1 and miR-1-2. Names are even preceded by the annotation for the species they are observed in e.g. *Homo sapiens* = hsa-miRxxx. Others include viral v-mirNA and *Drosophila* d-miRNA. microRNAs originating for the 3' end or 5' end are denoted with a -3p or 5p suffix e.g. miR-142-5p, miR-142-3p (Das 2012).

Mechanisms Underlying Biogenesis of MicroRNAs:

Being the ‘micromanagers of gene expression’, miRNAs made their first landmark as regulators of developmental events in a worm, *Caenorhabditis elegans*.

miRNA biogenesis, for the most part, occurs through the following sequential steps (Filipowicz, Bhattacharyya et al. 2008). miRNAs are encoded in the human genome as miRNA genes and are then processed to mature miRNAs. RNA polymerase II transcribes several-kilobyte-long fragments called primary miRNAs (pri-miRNAs), which are then capped and polyadenylated. The microprocessor complex, which is composed of the RNase III enzyme drossha and DGCR8, then cleaves the pri-miRNAs into ~70-nt-long premature miRNAs (pre-miRNA). The resulting pre-miRNAs are then exported to the cytoplasm through the Ran-GTP-dependent nuclear export factor exportin-5. Another RNase III enzyme, dicer, then cleaves the pre-miRNAs into 18- to 24-nt double-stranded RNAs. The resulting RNA-duplex associates with the miRNA-induced silencing complex (RISC), where one of the strands is degraded while the other becomes the mature miRNA. The mature miRNAs interact with target mRNAs via complementarity binding with a particular region known as “seed sequence.” The resultant

complex hinders assembly of ribosome, subsequently suppressing gene expression. An overview of the key processes involved in the biogenesis of miRNA is illustrated in **Fig. 1**.

Figure 1: MicroRNA (miRNA) biogenesis and post-transcriptional gene silencing mechanisms. pri-miRNA, primary miRNA; pre-miRNA, premature miRNA; RISC, miRNA-induced silencing complex.

[Adapted from “MicroRNAs in skin and wound healing” by Jaideep Banerjee, Yuk Cheung Chan, and Chandan K. Sen, *Physiol Genomics* 43: 543–556, 2011.]

MicroRNAs in Skin Morphogenesis:

The skin is made of three distinct layers of tissue (Shilo, Roy et al. 2007). The epidermis is populated mostly by keratinocytes along with dendritic cells, melanocytes, and Langerhans and Merkel cells. The dermis consists of collagenous and elastic fibers populated by fibroblasts, macrophages, mast cells, and lymphocytes. The dermis also consists of a glycosaminoglycan-proteoglycan fraction that functions as a supporting matrix or ground substance and makes up its base. It is composed of polysaccharides and protein that are linked to produce macromolecules and have important function in wound repair and tissue remodeling. Finally, the hypodermis is

composed of adipocyte lobules. The skin contains hair follicles, which are epidermal outgrowths and have a reservoir of stem cells that may regenerate the epidermis. The main functions of the skin include barrier defense, UV protection, thermoregulation, pigmentation, sensation of touch or pain, and regulation of water loss from the epidermis (Shilo, Roy et al. 2007) (Taylor, Lehrer et al. 2000).

Dicer, which is the miRNA processing enzyme, is present both in the epidermis as well as in the outer root sheath of the hair follicles. Skin miRNAs can be classified into distinct groups based on analogy in the 5' seed sequence of the miRNA (Lewis, Burge et al.) (Xie, Lu et al. 2005).

Based on the database of most abundantly expressed miRNAs in the skin, the miRNA-200 and miRNA-19/20 families are heavily expressed in the epidermis while the miRNA-199 family is abundantly expressed highly in the hair follicles (Yi, O'Carroll et al. 2006). This observation suggests that these miRNA families may have lineage-specific functions.

Recent studies underscore the importance of miRNAs in skin development and epidermal differentiation. Dicer depletion in the epidermis results in failure of production of mature miRNAs. A striking difference in the morphogenesis of hair follicle was observed when dicer was depleted in embryonic skin progenitor cells. Mutant mice carrying floxed dicer gene were crossed to CD-1 transgenic mice expressing Cre recombinase under the control of the human *keratin-14* promoter to obtain *dicer1^{fl/fl}*, K14-Cre (conditional knockout) mice. Follicular epithelium progenitors evaginated toward the surface of the skin into the epidermis instead of normal invagination toward the dermis (Schultz and Goldsmith) (Yi, O'Carroll et al. 2006). Loss of epithelial dicer affected both the epithelium and epithelial-mesenchymal signaling (Andl, Murchison et al. 2006).

In addition, absence of hair follicle stem cell marker expression and failure of dermal papilla and maintenance of the hair follicles were evidenced, resulting in stunted, hypoproliferative, and misoriented hair follicles (Andl, Murchison et al. 2006). Hyperproliferation also was noted in the epidermis (Andl, Murchison et al. 2006), which probably occurred because of arrest of physiological apoptosis, suggesting that the aging dicer-depleted skin might be susceptible to developing tumors. Dicer depletion also led to loss of expression of key signaling molecules such as sonic hedgehog (Shh) and Notch homolog 1 (Notch1) by postnatal day 7 (Andl, Murchison et al. 2006), which may be responsible for the hyperproliferative epidermal phenotype in the dicer-depleted epidermis. Inactivation of Notch1 has been also associated with hair loss followed by cyst formation, and thus Notch1 has emerged as a key miRNA-regulated protein in the skin that is silenced in response to dicer depletion, resulting in pathological conditions in the skin. Taken together, these data suggest that miRNAs are responsible for regulation of the genes involved in the development of the skin. Specific miRNAs required for the execution of key processes in skin morphogenesis have been identified (Proweller, Tu et al. 2006).

In addition to its role in miRNA biogenesis, dicer has been implicated in the biogenesis of other small RNAs like endogenous small interfering RNAs (endo-siRNAs) and small nuclear (sn)/small nucleolar (sno) small RNAs. Thus whether the observations from the dicer knockout approach may therefore be suited to study the significance of miRNAs remains an open question. The role of DGCR8, on the other hand, is wholly dedicated to miRNA biogenesis. Phenotypically, no significant differences were observed between knockouts of DGCR8 and dicer during embryonic skin development (Yi, Pasolli et al. 2009), thus establishing the fact that in the skin the primary functions of both the proteins is miRNA biogenesis and that miRNAs are essential for skin development.

The specific role of miRNA-203 in skin morphogenesis has been tested. miRNA-203 posttranscriptionally represses p63, which is crucial in initiation of epithelial stratification and maintenance of the proliferative potential of mature keratinocytes in the basal layers (Koster, Kim et al. 2004). p63 is strongly expressed in the innermost basal layer, the home of epithelial cells with high clonogenic and proliferative capacity (Senoo, Pinto et al. 2007). Mice lacking all p63 isoforms have no epidermis, squamous epithelia, or epithelial appendages (Mills, Zheng et al. 1999) (Yang, Kaghad et al. 1998). Thus p63 plays a key role in the formation of epidermis and other stratified epithelia. Between embryonic days 13.5 and 15.5, the expression of miRNA-203 levels in mouse suprabasal cells increases compared with that in basal cells, leading to silencing of p63 expression and thus stalling the proliferation of the epidermis (Koster, Kim et al. 2004). Although miRNA does not seem to completely silence p63 (Lena, Shalom-Feuerstein et al. 2008), it contributes as a switch between keratinocyte proliferation and differentiation in the adult epidermis. Recently, the mechanism for the induction of miRNA-203 has been reported. Ca²⁺, a protein kinase C (PKC) activator, is identified as an important signal in epidermal differentiation. Ca²⁺ regulates miRNA-203 expression in keratinocytes, and therefore miRNA-203 was expected to play an important role in development of the skin (Sonkoly, Wei et al. 1038). Specific inhibitors of PKC (GF109293X and Ro31-8220) were able to block such induction. Activator protein-1 (AP-1) proteins c-Jun and JunB were also found to be able to drive miRNA-203 expression in keratinocytes, thus suggesting that the upregulation of miRNA-203 is dependent on the activation of the PKC/AP-1 pathway (Sonkoly, Wei et al. 1038) (Yi, Poy et al. 2008).

MicroRNAs Regulating Skin Physiology:

MicroRNAs in maintenance of skin function. A key function of the skin is to serve as a first layer of defense against the outside environment. The epidermis is primarily responsible for this barrier function and also prevents loss of water from the organism. E-cadherin is an intercellular adhesion molecule that is specifically expressed in epithelial tissues and plays an important role in maintaining the epithelial architecture. E-cadherin is required for the maintenance of proper localization of key tight junctional proteins, and its absence results in permeable tight junctions compromising epidermal barrier function of the skin (Tinkle, Lechler et al. 2004). miRNA-200 and miRNA-205 are both highly expressed in normal skin and have been shown to specifically target ZEB1 and SIP1 (also known as ZEB2), the transcriptional repressors of E-cadherin (Gregory, Bert et al. 2008) (Korpal, Lee et al. 2008). Thus miRNA-200 and miRNA-205 are expected to positively regulate E-cadherin and seem to be essential in maintaining epithelial stability. However, it must be noted that these studies were performed in cell lines and transformed cells. Therefore the significance of these results in normal skin biology remains to be elucidated.

Another important function of the skin is pigmentation. Human pigmentation involves production and dispersion of melanin by epidermal melanocytes to neighboring keratinocytes (Kosmadaki, Naif et al.). Skin pigments are essential for absorbing the harmful ultraviolet radiations ~ 310 nm and also regulate skin vitamin D production (Neer 1975). miRNAs also have been reported to play a role in regulating skin pigmentation. miRNA profiling was done to compare expression in the skin of alpacas (domesticated species of South American camelids) with brown versus white coat color. Among the differentially expressed miRNAs, miRNA-25 repressed microphthalmia-associated transcription factor

(MITF) in skin melanocytes, which regulates genes linked to coat color like tyrosinase (tyr) and tyrosinase-related protein 1 (Zhu, He et al. 1016). Regulation of gene expression linked to skin color therefore has been identified as a novel functional role for miRNA-25. miRNA-434-5p is implicated in skin whitening and lightening by targeting tyr and hyaluronidase (hyal) genes. Tyr plays an essential role in melanin production, and therefore Tyr repression by miRNA-434-5p resulted in significant loss of black color in murine skin as well as hair (Wu, Chen et al. 2008).

Numerous publications attest to the importance of the developmental effects of miRNA-mediated regulation of gene expression. For example, miRNAs participate in the maternal-to-zygotic transition during early embryogenesis and affect the differentiation of many tissue types. In humans, miRNA disruption has been described in association with several cancers — a finding which has important implications for cancer aetiology, diagnosis and potentially for cancer treatment. miRNAs are increasingly becoming important as players in wound healing and tissue repairs (Banerjee and Sen 2013).

MicroRNA-XXX - the molecule of interest:

Figure 2: Screenshot from Gene databases of NCBI

Cell Culture & Antibodies:

Human Keratinocyte Culture Methods:

Normal human keratinocyte expresses *TERT* (telomerase reverse transcriptase), a protein-coding gene and grows well from low to moderate density platings in a medium commercially available from GIBCO/Invitrogen: “Keratinocyte serum-free medium (*GIBCO K-sfm*)” (*Invitrogen catalog #17005-042*).

Cells be thawed, expanded once and cryopreserved in *GIBCO K-sfm*, before trying any other media. Keratinocyte cultures growing in this medium essentially be subcultured before they have grown beyond 1/3 confluence.

It is important to subculture keratinocytes no more than 8 days after they have been plated, even if they have not reached the desired density. Cultures kept longer are harder to disaggregate with Trypsin/EDTA and do not replat as well.

For best results, common practices of many labs are to be avoided on serially passaging cell lines of plating **1:4** or **1:10** dilutions, this way we lose track of how well the cells are growing or will end up with cultures that become dense too soon.

GIBCO K-sfm medium was not designed to grow cells to high density. This can be switched to a medium consisting of a mixture of *GIBCO K-sfm* and a medium called “DF-K”.

Cultures that have grown to ~1/3 confluence in *GIBCO K-sfm* subsequently can be fed daily with a **1:1** mixture of *GIBCO K-sfm* and *DF-K*.

Human skin organ cultures and patient biopsies:

6mm punch biopsies were collected from healthy control individuals and atopic dermatitis patients. After fixing the skin sections with neutral buffered formalin, paraffin blocks were prepared and 5 µm sections were made on poly-lysine coated glass slides. For the isolation of total RNA, tissue was snap frozen immediately in liquid nitrogen and RNA was isolated by TRIzol reagent (Invitrogen, USA) as per manufacturer's protocol. After precipitating the RNA by isopropanol, the pellet was resuspended in Lysis solution (Exiqon, Denmark) and RNA isolation was carried out as discussed under the subheading "Total RNA isolation". Before performing miRNA microarray, the purity of samples was further validated by Agilent 2100 Bioanalyzer and samples with RIN number >4 were submitted for profiling.

Cell culture:

Normal human epidermal keratinocytes (NHEKs) immortalized with telomerase catalytic subunit – TERT (NTERT-1) (Dickson et al., 2000) were cultured in K-SFM (Invitrogen, USA) supplemented with 0.2 ng/ml of epidermal growth factor (EGF), 25 µg/ml of bovine pituitary extract (BPE), 0.4 mM CaCl₂ and Penicillin/Streptomycin (1X). Cultures were passaged before they reached 50% confluence regularly. For growing cells to high density (post-transfection), they were cultured in an equal ratio mixture of K-SFM and DF-K media (prepared by mixing calcium- and glutamine-free DMEM with Ham's F-12 at a ratio of 1:1 and supplementing with 0.2 ng/ml of EGF, 25 µg/ml BPE, 1.5 mM Glutamine and Penicillin/Streptomycin).

Total RNA isolation from cultured cells:

Total RNA was extracted using miRCURY™ RNA isolation kit (Exiqon, Denmark) and according to the manufacturer's protocol. Quality and purity of RNA was checked using NanoDrop ND-8000 spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific, USA).

miRNA microarray profiling (performed by Exiqon's miRNA Profiling Services):

The differential expression of miRNAs in skin samples was determined by subjecting the total RNA samples to miRCURY™ LNA Array (V5). A sample RNA pool containing an equal amount of all the RNA from different time points was used as a common reference pool and act as an internal control. The microarray data was normalized and miRNAs with significant differences compared to 0 hour time point sample (differential log mean ratio (dLMR) must be more or less than 1) were plotted as a heat map.

miRNA-specific real time RT-PCR:

Reverse transcription of miRNA to cDNA was performed using the Taqman® microRNA Reverse Transcription Kit (Applied Biosystems, USA) and following the Taqman® microRNA assay protocol. 20 ng of total RNA was used along with 3 µl of miRNA-specific RT primer per 15 µl reaction. The cDNA was diluted five-fold with nuclease-free water and 4 µl of cDNA was used along with miRNA real-time PCR primers (1X) and 5 µl of 2X Taqman® Fast Universal PCR master mix. PCR cycles were carried out at the following conditions, 94°C for 5 min (initial denaturation), 94°C for 30 sec and 60°C for 1 min for 40 cycles. Each miRNA candidate was normalized with U6 small nuclear RNA.

mRNA-specific real-time RT-PCR:

Reverse transcription of mRNA to cDNA was performed using the SuperScript® III First-Strand Synthesis System (Invitrogen, USA) according to manufacturer's protocol. 500 ng of total RNA was used as the starting material for cDNA synthesis.

This was followed by real-time amplification of cDNA using the Power SYBR® Green PCR Master Mix (Applied Biosystems, USA). The endogenous RNA control used for the skin biopsy samples and for the *in vitro* keratinocyte differentiation samples was different from the usual. The reason being the absolute values of GAPDH and Actin (the common RNA controls) transcript abundance were quite variable between samples despite taking equal concentration of total RNA, the reason for which is unclear at the moment. Hence RPLP0, a component of ribosomal subunit (which showed approximately equal Ct in both tissues and cells), was used for normalization of both the injury samples (n=3) and keratinocytes.

Immunohistochemistry (tissues) & Immunocytochemistry (Cells):

Immunohistochemical staining for YYY and K6A were performed on formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded skin biopsy sections. The steps in the staining of each protein were similar except for the different primary antibody (Abcam, USA) used. In brief, sections were deparaffinized in Xylene and rehydrated in a series of 100, 90, 80 and 70% ethanol and PBS. This was followed by immersion in 3% hydrogen peroxide in methanol for 30 min to quench endogenous peroxidase activity. Slides were then placed in a programmable pressure cooker for antigen retrieval in target retrieval solution (Dako, Denmark). The sections were treated with 10% goat serum (Dako) before incubating with the primary antibody against the respective proteins for 1 hour at room temperature. After washing with running water, incubation with the appropriate secondary antibody conjugated with Fluorescent conjugates was carried out for 30 min at room temperature. Slides were counterstained with DAPI and mounted using Floursave mounting media. For immunocytochemistry, cells were seeded on coverslips, washed twice with PBS,, fixed using Acetone/Methanol solution for 7 min followed by PBS wash. Cells were blocked with 10% goat serum and further steps are identical to immunocytochemistry except that PBS was used for washing instead of running tap water.

Transfection of negative and miR-XXX mimics:

Transfection was performed following a protocol by *Simpson et al.* that is optimized for NHEKs. Two sets of 10,000 and 50,000 NTERT cells were seeded onto six-well plates one to two days before transfection. 50 nM (final concentration) of each miRNA mimics (Dharmacon, USA) and 4 μ l of DharmaFECT 1 transfection reagent (Dharmacon) were added to 200 μ l K-SFM media without antibiotics separately and left for 5 min, before combining and leaving for another 30 min. 1600 μ l of the same media was then added to each tube and transferred to cells. After 24 hours, the transfection reaction mixture was replaced with DF-K media. For testing the effect of miRNA mimics on its targets, total RNA was isolated 48 hours post-transfection.

Cell cycle analysis:

Negative and miR-XXX transfected NTERTS were plated at a density of 100,000 cells/well and labeled with 10 μ M EdU for 4 hours, prior to harvesting the cells. Processing was done using Click-iT EdU Alexa Fluor 647 Flow cytometry assay (Invitrogen, USA). Cell nuclei were counterstained with 25 μ g/ml of Propidium iodide (Sigma-Aldrich, USA). Samples were subjected to EdU incorporation analysis using BD FACS Caliber (Becton Dickinson, USA). Data were analyzed using WIN-MDI 2.9 software.

Real time validation of shortlisted candidates:

Real time validation of shortlisted candidates (Cont.):

Figure 4: miRNAs showing down-regulation in AD patients' skin in the qPCR data. miR-XXX profile corresponded with the microarray data and fulfilled the selection criteria(s) in the bioinformatics screen.

Others showed down-regulation in qPCR data which did not correlate with microarray. Graphs are representative of three independent biological replicates. Error bars indicate standard error of mean.

Keys -

C: Control (Healthy Skin)

NL: Non Lesional Skin

LS: Lesional Skin

Note: qRT-PCR performed across 21 samples (3 healthy controls, 9 AD lesional skin, 9 AD non-lesional skin – See Appendix.

In-situ hybridization & Characterization of miR-XXX:

Figure 5: Images showing localization of miR-XXX in epidermis (in Healthy control, AD non lesional and lesional skins) – Assay performed by Sundaram G. M., PhD

Owing to the presence of multiple cell types in human skin (e.g. Keratinocytes, Langerhans, melanocytes) as well as multiple layers of epidermis, quantitative PCR (qPCR) would not be able to infer where the miRNA is expressed as in which layer(s) or cell type(s). To counter this, microRNA *in situ* hybridization was performed for miR-236 on human skin sections to monitor the spatiotemporal expression. As stained by **Fast Red** (stains red), miR-XXX lies in high levels at the epidermis of a healthy control. Levels of the same goes down significantly when AD – Non Lesional and AD - Lesional skin comes into picture. In agreement with qPCR data for the mature miRNAs, down-regulation of miR-XXX was seen in an **AD - Non Lesional skin** and repressed drastically in **AD – Lesional skin**. As the down-regulation of the candidate miRNA was observed throughout the whole distance of the epidermis, this indicated a global response triggered upon this infection.

Source of miR-XXX & its targets:

In order to gain insight into the source of miR-XXX, we looked at its genomic locus using UCSC genome browser (Fujita et al., 2010). MiR-XXX lies on the long arm of chromosome XX (qXX.X) and was found to be intronic. TargetScan analysis found 2 conserved Human YYY 3' UTR (YYY) targets of miRXXX and the screenshot is displayed in the next page.

Figure 8: YYY, the target of miR-XXX, up-regulated in AD – Lesional skin as detected by immunohistochemistry.

In order to validate, if protein YYY is an authentic target of miR-XXX, immunohistochemistry was performed on control healthy and AD lesional skin sections. As expected, protein YYY is expressed only in the basal layer of epidermis and very faint expression was observed in supra basal layers. This is in agreement with the inverse expression of miR-XXX in the epidermis, vis-a vis, higher expression in supra basal layer compared to basal layer (Fig 5), suggesting a mutually exclusive expression of miRNA and its target. In addition, AD lesional skin samples with down regulation of miR-XXX, abundant expression of protein YYY was observed and notably, the expression was extended even up to the top layers of supra basal epidermis. AS a control, we tested Keratin 6A, which is usually absent in interfollicular epidermis of normal skin (control healthy individual) is highly expressed in Atopic dermatitis lesional skin. Keratin 6A, being a hyperproliferative marker, suggest an hyperproliferative/ altered differentiation status of lesional skin compared to normal skin.

Transfection of miR-XXX mimics into keratinocytes:

Figure 9: On applying mimics into NTERTs by non-viral methods, cell viability does not seem to get affected in both the seeded population. Using various chemical, lipid or physical methods, this gene transfer technology is a powerful tool to study gene function and protein expression in the context of a cell.

Cell cycle checkpoint – G2/M cell cycle arrest in NTERTs:

Figure 10. miR-XXX treatment inhibits cell cycle progression in G2/M phase. Flow cytometric analysis shows an increase in the percentage of cells in the G2/M phase (cell cycle arrest), coupled with decrease in the S phase.

During this differentiation process, keratinocytes permanently withdraw from the cell cycle, initiate expression of epidermal differentiation markers, and move suprabasally as they become part of the stratum spinosum, stratum granulosum and eventually become corneocytes in the stratum corneum.

Cell cycle checkpoints are control mechanisms that ensure the fidelity of cell division in eukaryotic cells. These checkpoints verify whether the processes at each phase of the cell cycle have been accurately completed before progression into the next phase. While G₂/M checkpoint is passed, the cell initiates the many molecular processes that signal the beginning of mitosis. However, over expression of miR-XXX was found to induce G₂/M cell cycle arrest which is likely to happen during the normal differentiation of basal keratinocytes. Hence, this observation indicates that miRXXX may regulate the normal differentiation of keratinocytes in a healthy skin. It is tempting to speculate, the hyperproliferation/altered differentiation observed in AD lesional skin could likely be caused by the down regulation of miR-XXX.

Calcium Induced Differentiation of Keratinocytes:

Figure 11: Image in panel (A) shows normal proliferating Keratinocytes; (B) shows Ca²⁺ induced altered differentiating keratinocytes. Note the aggregation of cells to form tight stratifying colonies.

Figure 12: (A) Ca^{2+} triggered differentiation leading to higher levels of miR-XXX. (B) Levels of YYY, the target of miR-XXX, go down as Ca^{2+} triggers differentiation and miR-XXX goes up.

Figure 12: qPCR Data supporting Ca^{2+} triggered differentiation for detectors KRT10 and SPRR1A.

In order to test this hypothesis, it was essential to have a cell culture model for epidermal differentiation. Adding calcium to the medium of cultured keratinocytes elevates intracellular calcium and triggers differentiation. Intracellular calcium alters multiple signaling pathways, one of which is binding to calmodulin to activate the serine-threonine protein phosphatase calcineurin. Calcineurin dephosphorylates and activates the transcription factor NFAT and both calcineurin and NFAT are expressed in differentiating keratinocytes. Activated NFAT can regulate transcription through binding its own cognate DNA binding site. Another protein activated by calcium that may be involved in keratinocyte differentiation is Protein Kinase C (PKC). Hence, we standardized the conditions for optimal calcium induced differentiation in N/TERT cells. After trying different concentration of calcium chloride, 1.5mM calcium treatment for three days showed the stratification of cells, a process affiliated to normal differentiation of keratinocytes in skin. We further tested the calcium induced differentiation protocol using known markers of differentiation. Keratin 10, which is found only in supra basal layer of keratinocytes (differentiated) was seen upregulated upon calcium treatment within 3 days in two biological replicate samples. In addition, SPRR1A, a protein expressed in terminally differentiated

keratinocytes, at the granular layer in normal skin, was also induced upon calcium treatment, indicating that our protocol simulates normal differentiation program adopted by skin. Encouragingly, the expression of miR-XXX was also upregulated during calcium induced differentiation further supporting the notion that miR-XXX is required for normal differentiation of keratinocytes and calcium signaling is likely an upstream signaling event to trigger its expression. However, the induction of miR-XXX with Calcium treatment did not change the mRNA levels of protein YYY. This not surprising since miR-XXX may affect the translation of protein YYY instead of transcript degradation. Testing the protein levels of protein YYY will prove this point.

Discussion

miRNA-XXX has its global expression in healthy non patient skins. The candidate vanishes in patient skin samples with atopic dermatitis. TaqMan MicroRNA Low Density Arrays detect the same. Quantitative real-time PCR quantifies levels of expression in tissues and cells. *In situ* hybridization gives its cellular localization.

miR-XXX was one of the lowest-ranked downregulated miRNAs in patients with atopic dermatitis. In a healthy skin, it is predominantly expressed. miR-XXX gets downregulated during altered differentiation/hyperproliferation (pathological condition) Protein YYY, serving as a uniporter for glucose, was identified as a direct target of miR-XXX. Overexpression of miR-XXX in Telomerase transformed human keratinocytes (NTERTS) cells resulted in decreased YYY levels, accompanied by cell cycle arrest at G2/M stage.

miR-XXX is remarkably down regulated in patients with atopic dermatitis, absence of which may turn out as the trigger factor for altered differentiation in AD affected skins. This in turn shows higher expression of its direct target YYY which might contribute to chronic skin inflammation by increasing the proliferative response in keratinocytes.

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